

A Dissimilarity relational bipolar operator in the analysis of obesity-induced illness

G. Aruna¹ and J. Jesintha Rosline²

¹PG and Research Department of Mathematics, Auxilium College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Thiruvalluvar University, Serkkadu, Vellore Dist., Tamil Nadu, India.

²PG and Research Department of Mathematics, Auxilium College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Thiruvalluvar University, Serkkadu, Vellore Dist., Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract:

Fuzzy set theory and its extensions perform exceptionally well when managing ambiguous information. The bipolar fuzzy Set is one of the extensions that depict the positive and negative aspects of the data. In many fields, the bipolar fuzzy matrix effectively handles the data. In this artifact, we define a new dissimilarity relational operator of the bipolar fuzzy matrix. A novel algorithm is proposed using the new augmented operator. Additionally, we illustrate the suggested algorithm for identifying obesity-induced illness in the decision-making domain.

Keywords: Bipolar fuzzy set – Operator – score function- Obesity induced illness – decision making

Introduction:

Knowledge is an unending adventure at the edge of uncertainty says Jacob Bronowski. Zadeh's seminal work on Fuzzy set theory is in dealing with imprecise and uncertain information. Fuzzy sets are useful for decision-making in real-world situations with uncertain data. Atanassov (Atanassov, 1986) created the Intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) with a non-membership parameter [2]. IFS cannot be implemented if the sum of membership degree and the non-membership degree is greater than one. IFS have wide range of applications in various domains. To resolve the IFS issue, R. Yager [20] advances the Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) concept. Zhang (2016) introduced the idea of a bipolar fuzzy set to address a bipolar environment [21]. The bipolar fuzzy set is the extension of fuzzy set theory, which handles situations where positive and negative information coexist. This concept extends traditional fuzzy sets by incorporating both positive and negative membership degrees. Researchers developed the concepts of bipolar fuzzy set and applied in various field. Cuong suggested using a Picture fuzzy set to control a neutral environment [4]. Florentin Smarandache introduced the idea of the Neutrosophic fuzzy set to manage three additional parameters (Broumi et al., 2018)[16]. The evolution of bipolar fuzzy set and its properties made the researchers to incorporate it with other extensions of fuzzy set theory such as bipolar picture fuzzy set, Neutrosophic bipolar fuzzy set.

Decision-making is a crucial skill that significantly influences personal and professional development. It leads to fulfilling and successful outcomes in various aspects of life, including

career success, relationships, health, and financial stability. By adopting a structured and systematic approach, individuals can enhance their decision-making skills and achieve better outcomes. Fuzzy set theory is a widely used decision-making technique that helps expert systems to handle uncertain or imprecise information. It is particularly effective in medical diagnosis, financial forecasting, and risk assessment due to its ability to handle vague and ambiguous data. Fuzzy set theory, which uses linguistic variables and rules, makes it easier to understand and implement. This approach is particularly useful in medical diagnosing conditions that involve considering multiple symptoms and test results simultaneously, allowing for a comprehensive diagnosis. To provide a more accurate and nuanced diagnosis, bipolar fuzzy sets are helpful since they capture both the positive and negative parts of symptoms and criteria. This improves patient outcomes by improving diagnostic accuracy by taking into account degrees of membership rather than binary judgments. Several authors implemented the various properties of bipolar fuzzy set in the field of decision making.

Matrices are crucial in various domains, as traditional ones are insufficient for chaotic circumstances. Fuzzy matrices were first conceptualized by Hashimoto, to depict actual situations. In 1977, Thomason explored power convergence [19]. Many researchers established power series convergence, determinant, trace, transitive, and closure feature findings in fuzzy matrices [5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 13]. Cho researched regularity characteristics and rankings of fuzzy matrices in 1999 [3], and Pal studied fuzzy sets using different matrix ideas [7, 10, 18]. Pal introduced new operators in fuzzy matrices [17]. Pal (2016) enlarged fuzzy matrices with fuzzy rows and columns [14], established four binary fuzzy operators, and employed them for image processing. The eigenvectors and eigenvalues of bipolar fuzzy matrices were studied by Mondal and Pal (2016) [9]. A novel understanding of bipolar fuzzy matrices, their power convergence, and their applications has been explored by Pal and Sanjib (2019) [15]. Numerous researchers have employed the diverse characteristics of the bipolar fuzzy matrix in the domain of making decisions [1, 11].

In this artifact, Section 2 provides the basic definitions, characteristics, and functions of bipolar fuzzy set and bipolar fuzzy matrix. We define a novel dissimilarity relational operator of bipolar fuzzy set in Section 3. To determine the illness induced by obesity, we employed the new augmented operator in the MCDM problem in section 4. Section 5 presents the conclusion and the possible directions for further research.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 1: Bipolar fuzzy sets [21]

The bipolar fuzzy set $B = \{B^-, B^+\}$ is defined in universal set X . $B^+ \in [0, 1]$ is the satisfaction degree of x in B , $B^- \in [-1, 0]$ is the satisfaction degree of the implicit counter property of x in B .

Definition 2: Bipolar fuzzy matrix [15]

A bipolar fuzzy set is a pair of $M_b = M_{bij} = (-M_{bij}, M_{bij})$, where $(M_{b^-ij}, M_{b^+ij}) \in [0,1] \forall i, j$ are the negative and positive membership values of element M_{bij} respectively.

Definition 3: Operations on bipolar fuzzy matrix [9]

Let $M_1 = M_{a_{ij}} = (M_{a^-ij}, M_{a^+ij})_{p \times q}$, $M_2 = M_{b_{ij}} = (M_{b^-ij}, M_{b^+ij})_{q \times r}$ be two bipolar fuzzy matrix. Then

$$M_{a_{ij}} \odot M_{b_{ij}} = \left(\sum_{l=1}^m M_{1il} M_{2lj} \right)_{p \times r}$$

$$= \left(-\max \left[\min \left(M_{1^-il}, M_{2^-lj} \right) \right], \max \left[\min \left(M_{1^+il}, M_{2^+lj} \right) \right] \right)$$

Definition 4: Difference Operator [17]:

For $x_1, x_2 \in [0,1]$, the $\ominus$ operator is defined as,

$$x_1 \ominus x_2 = \begin{cases} x_1, & \text{if } x_1 > x_2 \\ 0, & \text{if } x_1 \leq x_2 \end{cases}$$

3. A new dissimilarity operator:**Definition 5: A dissimilarity relational operator:**

Let $b_1 = [b_1^-, b_1^+]$ and $b_2 = [b_2^-, b_2^+]$ be two bipolar fuzzy sets. A new operator $\ominus$ is defined as

$$b_1 \ominus b_2 = \begin{cases} b_1^+, b_1^+ > b_2^+ \\ b_1^-, b_2^- > b_1^- \\ 0, \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 6: Score function:

The score-valued function on the bipolar fuzzy set is defined as $\text{Score} = \mu^+ - \mu^-$, where $\text{Score} \in [-1, +1]$.

3.1 A novel algorithm in decision making:

Step 1: Consider the relative matrix (m_1) between the indicator sign of diseases and the diseases.

Step 2: Consider the relative matrix (m_2) between patients and indicator sign.

Step 3: Compute the complementary matrix m_1^c .

Step 4: Compute the complementary matrix m_2^c .

Step 5: Compute the matrix, $m_3 = m_2 \odot m_1^c$ which represents the relation between the patients and diseases.

Step 6: Compute the matrix, $m_4 = m_2^c \odot m_1^c$ which represents the non- relation between the patients and diseases.

Step 7: Using the new dissimilarity operator we can calculate the matrix m_5 representing the maximum likelihood of the disease's existence.

Step 8: Calculate the matrix m_6 using a score- valued function. The highest score indicating the disease's potential.

4. Applications:

In fuzzy set theory, Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) entails evaluating and making decisions based on ambiguous, subjective, or imprecise information. BFS is an adaptable framework for decision-making that can manage stakeholders' positive and negative viewpoints, guaranteeing a fair result in complicated situations with divergent perspectives. Five individuals $I = \{I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_5\}$ are experiencing obesity due to various factors R including $r_1 =$ poor diet, $r_2 =$ lack of physical activity, $r_3 =$ family factors, $r_4 =$ psychological factors, and $r_5 =$ socioeconomic factors. The obesity induce illness, including $\delta_1 =$ poor self-esteem, $\delta_2 =$ abdominal fat, $\delta_3 =$ high cholesterol, $\delta_4 =$ breathing issues, and $\delta_5 =$ fatty liver disease.

Step 1:

Let γ_1 be the matrix that represents the relation between reasons and obesity induced illness.

$$\gamma_1 = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ r_4 \\ r_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (-0.7,0.5) & (-0.1,0.6) & (-0.3,0.2) & (-0.4,0.7) & (-0.6,0.4) \\ (-0.9,0.6) & (-0.5,0.8) & (-0.6,0.4) & (-0.3,0.5) & (-0.7,0.3) \\ (-0.8,0.4) & (-0.7,0.3) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.9,0.4) & (-0.6,0.2) \\ (-0.4,0.5) & (-0.6,0.7) & (-0.8,0.1) & (-0.7,0.6) & (-0.5,0.8) \\ (-0.3,0.1) & (-0.4,0.8) & (-0.9,0.6) & (-0.5,0.2) & (-0.4,0.5) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 2:

Let γ_2 be the matrix that represents the relation between individual and reasons.

$$\gamma_2 = \begin{matrix} & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 & r_4 & r_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{ccccc} (-0.6,0.4) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.5,0.3) & (-0.5,0.2) & (-0.3,0.7) \\ (-0.1,0.7) & (-0.4,0.3) & (-0.7,0.8) & (-0.6,0.4) & (-0.5,0.4) \\ (-0.5,0.9) & (-0.6,0.2) & (-0.4,0.1) & (-0.8,0.7) & (-0.7,0.8) \\ (-0.8,0.3) & (-0.7,0.5) & (-0.1,0.4) & (-0.3,0.6) & (-0.9,0.7) \\ (-0.5,0.2) & (-0.8,0.4) & (-0.6,0.8) & (-0.4,0.9) & (-0.8,0.6) \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Step 3:

The complement matrix of γ_1 represents the relation between non- reason for obesity and obesity induced illness.

$$\gamma_1^c = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} r_1 \\ r_2 \\ r_3 \\ r_4 \\ r_5 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{ccccc} (-0.3,0.5) & (-0.9,0.4) & (-0.7,0.8) & (-0.6,0.3) & (-0.4,0.6) \\ (-0.1,0.4) & (-0.5,0.2) & (-0.4,0.6) & (-0.7,0.5) & (-0.3,0.7) \\ (-0.2,0.6) & (-0.3,0.7) & (-0.5,0.3) & (-0.1,0.6) & (-0.4,0.8) \\ (-0.6,0.5) & (-0.1,0.3) & (-0.2,0.9) & (-0.3,0.4) & (-0.5,0.2) \\ (-0.7,0.9) & (-0.6,0.2) & (-0.1,0.4) & (-0.5,0.8) & (-0.6,0.5) \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Step 4:

The complement matrix of γ_2 represents the relation between non reasons for obesity and individuals.

$$\gamma_2^c = \begin{matrix} & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 & r_4 & r_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{array}{ccccc} (-0.4,0.6) & (-0.5,0.3) & (-0.1,0.7) & (-0.5,0.8) & (-0.7,0.3) \\ (-0.9,0.3) & (-0.6,0.7) & (-0.3,0.2) & (-0.4,0.6) & (-0.5,0.6) \\ (-0.5,0.1) & (-0.4,0.8) & (-0.6,0.9) & (-0.2,0.3) & (-0.3,0.2) \\ (-0.2,0.7) & (-0.3,0.5) & (-0.9,0.6) & (-0.7,0.4) & (-0.1,0.3) \\ (-0.5,0.8) & (-0.1,0.6) & (-0.4,0.2) & (-0.6,0.1) & (-0.2,0.4) \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Step 5:

Compute the matrix γ_3 that represents the relation between individual and obesity induced illness.

$$\gamma_3 = \gamma_2 \odot \gamma_1 = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (-0.8,0.6) & (-0.7,0.7) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.9,0.5) & (-0.6,0.5) \\ (-0.7,0.5) & (-0.7,0.6) & (-0.6,0.7) & (-0.7,0.7) & (-0.6,0.4) \\ (-0.6,0.5) & (-0.8,0.8) & (-0.8,0.6) & (-0.7,0.7) & (-0.6,0.7) \\ (-0.7,0.5) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.9,0.6) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.7,0.6) \\ (-0.9,0.5) & (-0.6,0.7) & (-0.8,0.7) & (-0.6,0.6) & (-0.7,0.8) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 6:

Compute the matrix γ_4 that represents the relation between individual and non – illness grade of obesity.

$$\gamma_4 = \gamma_2^c \odot \gamma_1^c = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (-0.7,0.6) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.4,0.8) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.6,0.7) \\ (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.9,0.8) & (-0.7,0.6) & (-0.6,0.6) & (-0.5,0.7) \\ (-0.3,0.6) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.4,0.3) \\ (-0.6,0.5) & (-0.3,0.7) & (-0.5,0.7) & (-0.3,0.5) & (-0.5,0.6) \\ (-0.6,0.5) & (-0.5,0.4) & (-0.5,0.8) & (-0.5,0.5) & (-0.5,0.6) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 7:

Compute γ_5 using the new dissimilarity relational bipolar operator.

$$\gamma_5 = \gamma_3 \ominus \gamma_4 = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} (-0.8,0) & (-0.7,0) & (-0.5,0) & (-0.9,0) & (0,0) \\ (-0.7,0) & (0,0) & (0,0.7) & (-0.7,0.7) & (-0.6,0) \\ (-0.6,0) & (-0.8,0.8) & (-0.8,0) & (-0.7,0.7) & (-0.6,0.7) \\ (-0.7,0) & (-0.5,0) & (-0.9,0) & (-0.5,0.6) & (-0.7,0) \\ (-0.9,0) & (-0.6,0.7) & (-0.8,0) & (0,0.8) & (-0.7,0.8) \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 8:

Applying the score function, we calculate γ_6 .

$$\gamma_6 = \begin{matrix} & \delta_1 & \delta_2 & \delta_3 & \delta_4 & \delta_5 \\ \begin{matrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0.8 & 0.7 & 0.5 & 0.9 & 0 \\ 0.7 & 0 & 0.7 & 0 & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 0 & 0.8 & 0 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 0.5 & 0.9 & 0.1 & 0.7 \\ 0.9 & 0.1 & 0.8 & 0 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Figure 1: Representation of disease potential level

4.1 Results and Discussions:

Figure 1, depicts that I_1 can be affected by the breathing illness (δ_4). And I_2 can be affected by high cholesterol (δ_3), and poor self-esteem (δ_1) issues. While I_3 and I_4 can be affected with high cholesterol (δ_3). I_5 can be affected by poor self-esteem (δ_1) issues. This procedure is quite helpful for our application in real life.

5. Conclusion:

Bipolar fuzzy sets (BFS) allow for the simultaneous assessment of preferences and rejections in model instances. BFS is intended for use in decision-making procedures that take into consideration both positive and negative information. A novel bipolar fuzzy set dissimilarity operator is defined in this artifact. A new algorithm is proposed with the help of a new dissimilarity operator. Additionally, the suggested technique is employed in decision-making to identify illnesses spurred on by obesity. The forthcoming investigation will explore the features of bipolar fuzzy relations and their uses in various disciplines.

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